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Measurement of the Natural Radioactivity in Cataclastic Rock Samples using RS-230 Spectrometer

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Natural radioactivity levels for radioactive samples occurring in construction material have been carried out for forty cataclastic rock samples from Abu Rusheid area in the Eastern Desert. In the present study the concentrations of ²³⁸U, ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K (%) were measured using RS-230 gamma ray spectrometer with high accuracy. Radiation exposure rate, absorbed dose rate and the annual absorbed dose rate were calculated from the measured concentrations of natural radioactivity. From the results, the concentration of uranium in ppm ranged from 1.80 to 222.60 and thorium ranged from 2.40 to 487.40 ppm. The values of radiation exposure rate ranged from 2.88 to 245.97 μRh^{-1} and the annual absorbed dose rate ranged from 0.24 to 20.50 mSvy^{-1} . The values of the absorbed dose rate are higher than the acceptable limit. From the obtained results, we can conclude that the area under study can be used as a mine of natural radioactive elements.

Keywords: Radioactivity, ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, Exposure, Dose.

INTRODUCTION

The earth's crust generally contains concentrations of uranium of the order of 0.5-5 ppm and thorium of the order of 2-20 ppm. The average activity concentration of ²³²Th is in the range of 25-50 Bqkg^{-1} . Concentration of natural radionuclides in the environment differ from one sample to another depending on the nature of the sample, its chemical composition, its density, sampling site and collection depth (Lakehal et al, 2010). Gamma radiation depends primarily on the geological and geographical conditions and appears at different levels in the soil of each region in the world (Tufail et al, 2006). The components of natural environments such as soils, rocks, sediments, vegetation, air and water include some naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM). These materials may contain ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, their radioactive daughters and the primordial radioactive isotope ⁴⁰K. These radionuclides give rise to internal and external radiation exposures, both indoor and outdoor. The activity concentration levels of naturally occurring radionuclides in soils are essential for an accurate assessment of possible radiological risks to human health in this region (Oladele, 2009). The composition of the radiation environment, the ranges of the different radioactivity concentrations and their dose contributions is the basis on which significance of additional radionuclide pollutions and their biological effects can be evaluated. The occurrence of natural radioactivity especially of the primordial radionuclides of ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U series, ²³²Th and its daughter products in the near surface regions of the Earth crust is highly uneven, leading to a varying radiation dose to the population. Various living conditions and habits give another dimension to the variety of these doses. Major radionuclides of importance in assessing environmental radiological contamination as a consequence of among processing include ⁴⁰K, ²³⁸U, ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th. Among these, ²²⁶Ra has been the reference radionuclide in assessing radiological risk (Ismail, 2007). Measurements of nuclear material are important in many areas of environmental studies; for nuclear material, an initial basic characterization of the material is important (IAEA Report 115, 1996).

Therefore, the natural environmental radiation mainly depends on geological and geographical conditions. Higher radiation levels are associated with igneous rocks, such as granite and lower levels with sedimentary rocks.

There are exceptions, however, as some shale and phosphate rocks have a relatively high content of radionuclides (Nadia, 2008).

The present work aimed to determine the distribution and intensities of uranium (^{238}U), thorium (^{232}Th), radium (^{226}Ra) and potassium (^{40}K) in the area under study. Calculate the exposure rate, annual effective dose and absorbed dose rate. In order to assess the radiological risk associated with among processing and the accumulated effluent in the studied area and to assess any change in radioactivity background levels due to various geological processes or any influences on the radiation environment.

The study region of Abu Rusheid area is a distinctive occurrence of uranyl mineralization in Egypt where the host rocks are represented by cataclastic rocks. The study area lies in the southern part of the Eastern Desert of Egypt, along the lower reaches of Wadi Abu Rusheid. It is located about 45 km southwest of Marsa Alam, between latitude $24^{\circ} 36' 43''$ and $24^{\circ} 38' 26''$ N and longitude $34^{\circ} 46' 00''$ and $34^{\circ} 46' 35''$ E. The area could be reached from the Red Sea coast through Wadi Al Gemal and then Wadi Nugrus along a desert track about 40 km long (Figure1).

1.1. Pan African Rock Units at Abu Rusheid

Abu Rusheid area is located between a major thrust to the NE and a minor one to the SW. The main rock units encountered in this area are metasediments, ophiolitic mélangé, amphibolites, metagabbros, cataclastic rocks and leuco- and pink granites (Saleh, G.M. 1997). Although Abu Rusheid gneisses were originally identified as psammitic gneisses (Hassan, M.A. 1973), some authors described these rocks as gneissic granites (Ibrahim et al, 2004) and cataclastic granites (Ibrahim et al, 2011). Furthermore, the geochemical data of these gneisses suggest sedimentary protolithes ranging from lithic arenite to arkose (Saleh et al, 2010). The depositional environment of this sedimentary protolithes was in an active continental margin setting (Roser and Korsch, 1986). Abu Rusheid cataclastic rocks are highly mylonitized and dissected by several shear zones mostly oriented to north and north east directions. Brecciation resulting from faulting reactivation is found in some parts along the shear zones. The cataclastic rocks show a well developed planar banding, gneissosity and folding. Lineation, defined by mineral streaking is well marked on the foliation surfaces. Small size quartz and pegmatitic veins are common and seem to be developed from the gneiss through mobilization and crystallization as they fade out into the gneiss with no sharp contacts. These pegmatite veins are abundant along Khour Abalea shear zone. Petrographically, Abu Rusheid cataclastic rocks are composed mainly of quartz, in addition to feldspars, biotite and muscovite with minor zircon, garnet, sulphides, apatite, monazite, uranium-rich thorite and magnetite (Saleh, G.M. 1997). Furthermore, ishkawaite, uranium-rich samarskite [U, Fe, Y, Ca) (Nb, Ta) O₄] in these rocks were reported by (Ibrahim et al, 2004). The detailed geologic map of the study area is characterized by low to moderate topography. The tectonostratigraphic sequence of the precambrian rocks unit of the studied area (Figure 1) are arranged as follows:

- i) Ophiolitic mélangé, consisting of ultramafic rocks and layered metagabbros set in metasediment matrix.
- ii) Cataclastic rocks, consisting of protomylonites, mylonites, ultramylonites and silicified ultramylonites.
- iii) Mylonitic granites.
- iv) Post-granite dykes and veins.

The secondary uranium mineralization occurs as micro-fractures infilling or coating on joint surfaces and represented by kasolite, curite, boltwoodite, coffinite, carnotite, uranyl silicate (uranophane, soddyite), torbernite, autunite and meta-autunite and ishkawaite veins (Ibrahim et al, 2004), (Saleh et al, 2010).

Fig. 1 A location map and detailed geologic map of Abu Rusheid area, South Eastern Desert, Egypt (Ibrahim et al., 2004)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Forty locations were measured in the area under study. Distance between two locations is about 250 meters. The studied rock samples were investigated radiometrically in the field using RS-230 BGO Super-Spec portable radiation detector, handheld unit spectrometer survey meter with high accuracy and its probable measurement errors was about 5%.

The new RS-230 Spectrometer is the state-of-the art in portable hand-held radiation spectrometer survey instrument for the Geophysical industry. It offers an integrated design with full weather protection, large detector, ease of use and the highest sensitivity in the market segment. This detector is full assay capability with data in K%, U (ppm), Ra (ppm) and Th (ppm), no radioactive sources required for proper operation. The detector is independent private company (Radiation Solutions Inc, 386 Watline Ave, Mississauga, Ontario, Canada, L4Z 1X2).

The detector was calibrated before it was used. The calibration is the procedure that establishes the proportionality between measured counts and ground concentrations of Potassium, Uranium and Thorium. This procedure enables the use of the spectrometer to make qualitative determinations of U, Th and K compositions of surface rocks and soils. Both airborne and ground instruments are calibrated using international standards developed by the Geological Survey of Canada (GSC) that are traceable to the IAEA in Vienna. These standards ensure consistent, accurate estimates of K, U and Th. Uranium, thorium and potassium in rocks are sources of gamma radiation. Their effects in the air can be expressed in terms of exposure rate or absorbed dose rate by using the conversion factors from radioelement concentrations in the samples to exposure rate or absorbed dose rate. The

ground level exposure rate can be calculated from the apparent concentrations of K (%), eU (ppm), and eTh (ppm) using the expression (IAEA Report 323, pp 97, 1991), (El-Galy et al, 2008):

$E (\mu\text{R h}^{-1}) = 1.505 K (\%) + 0.653 \text{ eU (ppm)} + 0.287 \text{ eTh (ppm)}$. (1) Exposure rate can be converted from ($\mu\text{R h}^{-1}$) to (pGys^{-1}) as follows (El-Galy et al, 2008), IAEA Report 566, pp 48 (1990):

$$1 \mu\text{R h}^{-1} = 2.4139 \text{ pGys}^{-1}. (2)$$

From the last equation (2) we get on:

$$1 \mu\text{R h}^{-1} = 8.69 \text{ nGy h}^{-1}. (3)$$

Different types of radiations cause different effects in biological tissues. For this reason, in comparing the effects of radiation on a living system, a derived unit, the roentgen equivalent man (rem) is used. One rem is the dose from any radiation that produces biological affects in a man. The conversion from exposure rate (E) to dose (D) rate is given by (El-Galy et al, 2008), (Grasty et al, 1991):

$D (\text{mrem y}^{-1}) = 8.33 E (\mu\text{R h}^{-1})$. (4) In recent years, quantities used in radiation protection have more commonly been expressed by the sievert (Grasty et al, 1991):

$$D^\circ (\text{mSv y}^{-1}) = 0.0833 \times E (\mu\text{R h}^{-1}) (5)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The content in (ppm) for different nuclides (U, Th, Ra) and K% for forty locations are given in Table 1 in the area under investigation. From table the values of ^{238}U ranged from 1.80 to 222.60 ppm, while the concentration of ^{232}Th ranged from 2.40 to 487.40 ppm and the radium content ranged from 42 to 277 ppm. From the results it is clear that the concentration of ^{232}Th is higher than ^{238}U . The obtained results for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th are higher than the acceptable levels of UNSCEAR (2000) and the values of potassium (K%) is high in all locations. The ratios of U/Ra and Th/U were calculated. The uranium content and Th/U ratios in rock samples are useful for deducing the conditions under which the highly anomalous mineralized or uraniferous types were formed and the values ranged from 0.78 to 10.75. The eU/eRa ratios reflected a state of radioactive equilibrium between uranium and its daughter. The values of eU/eRa ratios were ranged from 0.01 to 2.69. It is clear that the activity ratios in most samples in the ^{238}U series are less than unity. Figure 2 shows the relation between the sample number and the uranium concentration in (ppm) while, Figure 3 gives the relation between the sample number and the thorium concentration in (ppm). The relation between sample number and concentration of (K%) is given by Figure 4.

Table 1. The content of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{226}Ra in (ppm), concentration of ^{40}K (%), and the ratios of U/Ra, Th/U, of the rock samples, Abu Rusheid, SED, Egypt.

Sample No.	^{40}K (%)	^{238}U (ppm)	^{232}Th (ppm)	^{226}Ra (ppm)	eU /eRa	eTh/eU
1	4.70	20.20	57.50	189	0.11	2.85
2	4.90	98.70	281.40	80	1.23	2.85
3	4.70	89.10	314.60	99	0.90	3.53
4	5.80	133.90	317.90	277	0.48	2.37
5	4.40	73.40	417.50	195	0.38	5.69
6	5.30	188.40	400.60	70	2.69	2.13
7	4.00	45.40	199.10	90	0.50	4.39
8	3.40	48.80	125.90	125	0.39	2.58
9	4.00	53.30	203.80	149	0.36	3.82
10	5.90	63.10	455.40	56	1.13	7.22
11	3.60	34.80	27.00	104	0.33	0.78
12	5.60	69.60	324.40	120	0.58	4.66
13	3.80	61.80	93.30	97	0.64	1.51
14	5.50	141.20	455.50	130	1.08	3.22

15	3.70	32.40	230.50	243	0.13	7.11
16	4.00	30.60	56.30	102	0.30	1.84
17	4.30	31.60	261.80	70	0.45	8.28
18	4.50	60.70	223.50	125	0.49	3.68
19	4.20	55.70	282.40	101	0.55	5.07
20	5.60	78.60	389.70	56	1.40	4.96
21	5.30	51.20	307.40	116	0.44	6.00
22	5.10	222.60	217.90	113	1.97	0.98
23	4.70	28.90	310.60	65	0.44	10.75
24	6.80	37.10	141.60	91	0.41	3.82
25	5.20	31.50	214.00	67	0.47	6.80
26	0.30	5.30	5.70	63	0.08	1.07
27	5.30	119.00	391.80	230	0.52	3.30
28	4.20	40.50	216.00	227	0.18	5.33
29	0.70	2.80	8.60	139	0.02	3.07
30	5.10	134.80	487.40	144	0.94	3.62
31	3.20	53.90	198.10	121	0.45	3.67
32	3.00	43.00	141.00	194	0.22	3.29
33	4.00	57.40	442.90	192	0.30	7.72
34	3.50	37.60	230.00	87	0.43	6.12
35	0.50	1.80	6.20	206	0.01	3.44
36	3.80	49.70	323.90	258	0.19	6.52
37	0.50	2.20	2.40	67	0.03	1.10
38	5.20	59.60	429.70	42	1.42	7.21
39	0.10	3.00	6.00	133	0.02	2.00
40	4.90	52.00	373.00	221	0.24	7.17

Table 2 gives the values of exposure rate, effective dose rate, annual effective dose rate and absorbed dose rate of the samples. The values of the radiation exposure rate were ranged from 2.88 to 245.97 μRh^{-1} and the annual absorbed dose rate ranged from 0.24 to 20.50 mSvy^{-1} .

Table 2. The values of exposure rate, effective dose rate, annual effective dose rate and absorbed dose rate of the rock samples, Abu Rusheid, SED, Egypt.

Sample No.	Exposure rate (μRh^{-1})	Effective dose rate (μSvh^{-1})	Annual effective dose rate (mSvy^{-1})	Absorbed dose rate (nGyh^{-1})
1	36.77	0.39	3.06	319.53
2	152.58	1.60	12.71	1325.92
3	155.55	1.70	12.96	1351.72
4	187.40	2.00	15.61	1628.51
5	174.37	1.90	14.53	1515.28
6	245.97	2.60	20.50	2137.48
7	92.81	1.00	7.73	806.52
8	73.12	0.78	6.09	635.41
9	99.31	1.10	8.27	863.04
10	180.78	2.00	15.06	1571.00
11	35.89	0.37	3.00	311.90
12	146.98	1.60	12.24	1277.25
13	72.85	0.77	6.07	633.08
14	231.21	2.50	19.26	2009.21
15	92.88	1.00	7.74	807.12
16	43.26	0.45	3.60	375.96
17	102.25	1.10	8.52	888.49
18	110.55	1.20	9.21	960.72

19	123.74	1.40	10.31	1075.32
20	171.60	1.90	14.29	1491.18
21	129.63	1.40	10.80	1126.52
22	215.57	2.30	17.96	1873.31
23	115.08	1.30	9.60	1000.11
24	75.10	0.81	6.56	652.61
25	89.81	0.98	7.48	780.48
26	5.48	0.58	0.46	47.65
27	198.13	2.10	16.50	1721.75
28	94.76	1.00	7.90	823.46
29	5.35	0.57	0.45	46.49
30	235.58	0.2.6	19.62	2047.22
31	96.86	1.10	8.07	841.78
32	73.06	0.79	6.08	634.90
33	170.61	1.90	14.21	1482.64
34	31.60	1.10	2.63	274.60
35	3.71	0.39	2.68	32.22
36	131.13	1.40	10.92	1139.54
37	2.88	0.30	0.24	25.01
38	170.07	1.90	14.17	1477.90
39	3.83	0.39	0.32	33.30
40	148.38	1.60	12.36	1289.44

The values of the absorbed dose rate ranged from 25.01- 2137.48 nGyh⁻¹ and effective absorbed dose rate ranged from 0.30 to 2.60 μ Svh⁻¹. The values of the absorbed dose rate were higher than the acceptable limits, which are recommended by UNSCEAR (2000). Figure 5 shows the relation between the sample number and radiation exposure rate in (μ Rh⁻¹). The relation between the sample number and effective dose rate in (μ Svh⁻¹) is given by Figure 6, because the effective dose rate signals potential environmental radiological risks in the studied area.

Fig. (2) The relation between the sample No. and uranium concentration in (ppm)

Fig.(3)The relation between the sample No. and thorium concentration in (ppm)

Fig.(4) The relation between the sample No. and concentration of K-40

Fig. (5) The relation between the sample No. and radiation exposure rate ($\mu\text{R/h}$)

Fig. (6) The relation between the sample No. and the effective dose rate ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$)

CONCLUSION

Radioactivity levels of the environment depend on geological aspects of rock samples, where they are found in varying concentrations. The chemical and physical alterations play their role in the redistribution of radionuclides in different rock types which were subjected to these alteration processes. This distribution of radionuclides reflects its impacts on the environment.

From the results the concentration of uranium in ppm ranged from 1.80 to 222.60 and thorium ranged from 2.40 to 487.40 ppm. The values of radiation exposure rate ranged from 2.88 to 245.97 $\mu\text{R/h}^{-1}$, the annual absorbed dose rate ranged from 0.24 to 20.50 mSv^{-1} and the absorbed dose rate ranged from 25.01 to 2137.48 nGy^{-1} . The

values of the absorbed dose rate are higher than the permissible average world limit, which was recommended by UNSCEAR (2000). The bulk of the dose to the world's population has its average value as 2.5 mSv y^{-1} and also is responsible for the great variety of these values ranging from 1 to 100 mSv y^{-1} , the recommended limit 20 mSv y^{-1} ICRP Report 21, 1-3 (1991). The comparison between the obtained results with the international published data is shown in Table (3).

The information gathered will be very useful to determine the radiological impact of among processing activities, especially those activities that employ recycling mining management systems and invaluable in future considerations for land use development in affected areas. The distribution of radionuclide activity concentrations in the rock samples varieties affect the values of the absorbed dose rate in the studied rocks which are higher than the worldwide limit and are not safe for humans. This means that these rocks are not safe for human beings from the environmental point of view. The exposure and dose rates exceeded public permissible values in the sedimentary rock samples so that we must use personal protective masks to protect ourselves from inhalation of alpha particles and don't live near the area under study to minimize the exposure time of radiation.

This work permits us to make the first steps in establishing a database reference of natural radionuclide concentrations. The objective was to estimate the activity concentrations of natural radionuclides consisting of mainly ^{40}K and the natural radioactive series ^{238}U and ^{232}Th in the studied area. From the obtained results we can conclude that the area under study can be used as a mine of natural radioactive elements.

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Table 3. Comparison between the obtained results with the international published data from different countries

Country	Sample	⁴⁰ K (%)	²³⁸ U (ppm)	²³² Th (ppm)	²²⁶ Ra (ppm)	D° (mSvy ⁻¹)	D (nGyh ⁻¹)	References
Egypt	Rocks	0.71	310	12	280	8-25		(El Galy et al. 2008)
Egypt	Rocks	1.70-11.50					23.40-154.30	(Jose Araujo, et al., 2005)
Egypt	Rocks						100.48 - 22140.53	(Nadia, 2008)
Egypt	Dolostones Sandstone Argillaceous	0.29 0.3 0.93	418.69 8.34 276.88	3.14 4.68 11.47	808.75 7.88 419.49		58.61–21870.42 15.30–139.49 80.23–19492.07	(Ibrahim et al., 2011)
Egypt	Marble Granite						2.45 - 64.44 41.55 - 111.94	(Walley El Dine et al., 2001)
Egypt	Phos.mine		30 - 260					(Bigu, et al., 2000)
Egypt	Salt						1.46 –16.13	(El-Bahi, 2003)
Brazil	Rocks		2.90 – 37.00					(Amaral et al., 2012)
Cyprus	Rocks	0.60 ± 0.10	2.80 ± 0.70	1.30 ± 0.30			0.10- 50.00	(Michalis et al., 2003)
Nigeria	Soil						12.42- 451.33	(Oladele, 2009)
Brazil	Granite	0.60- 6.40	0.4 -13.00	1.10 – 110.00				(Anjos et al., 2005)
Italy	Soil	1.90-2.50						(Tzortzis and Tsertos, 2004)
India	Soil	200-854					9 - 37	(Kannan et al., 2002)
Kenya	Soil						69.5	(Mustapha et al., 1999)
IAEA	Public Occupational					5 20		(IAEA,1996)
UNSCEAR	Av. World					2.4	30	UNSCEAR, (2000)
ICRP	Av. Limit					20		(ICRP, 1997)
Egypt	Cataclastic rocks	0.10- 6.80	1.80-222.60	2.40-487.40	56-277	0.24 20.50	25 -2137.48	The present study

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